

ARTICEL TITLE: *Association of heavy menstrual bleeding with cardiovascular disease in US female hospitalizations.*

ABSTRACT:

This article examines the relationship between heavy menstrual bleeding (HMB) and cardiovascular disease (CVD) in hospitalized women in the US. The authors emphasize that HMB is one of the most common menstrual disorders, often coexisting with other conditions such as anemia, obesity, hormonal imbalances, and insulin resistance, and may represent an important but previously underappreciated risk signal for heart disease in women. The aim of the study was to determine whether HMB, both in the presence and absence of irregular menstruation (IM), is associated with an increased likelihood of cardiovascular events during hospitalization.

A population of 2.43 million hospitalized women, with an average age of approximately 40 years, was included in the analysis. Table 1 presents detailed demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population, revealing significant differences between women with HMB and the control group with normal cycles (NCM). Women with HMB were, on average, younger, and they were significantly more likely to have excess body weight, low hemoglobin levels, ovulatory disorders, and uterine fibroids. They were less likely to have metabolic syndrome, hypertension, or diabetes, largely due to their younger age. However, in the group of women ≤ 40 years of age, these differences were even more pronounced and included higher rates of insulin resistance and metabolic disorders.

The key results are presented in Figure 1, where in women ≤ 40 years of age, heavy menstrual periods were associated with significantly greater susceptibility to cardiovascular events, both those affecting coronary blood flow and myocardial function. Even after controlling for a broad set of variables such as age, race, socioeconomic status, obesity, PCOS, anemia, and use of hormonal contraceptives, metabolic syndrome for HMB remained an independent risk factor.

Table 2 provides particularly interesting data, distinguishing between HMB without IM and HMB with IM. Particularly strong associations were observed among women with heavy but regular cycles, as their risk of cardiovascular events was significantly higher. However, when heavy bleeding was accompanied by irregular cycles, the association was limited to individual heart diseases. This means that, contrary to previous beliefs that ovulation disorders are the primary risk factor, HMB alone proved to be a stronger predictor of CVD than HMB resulting from IM. This result is of significant clinical significance, as it suggests that HMB may be an early marker of vascular or hemostatic disorders independent of hormonal imbalances.

The authors conducted numerous sensitivity analyses, excluding patients with PCOS, fibroids, and congenital heart disease, as well as lifestyle factors such as smoking, alcohol, and obesity. Removing further potential confounding factors did not weaken the observed association; in fact, in some cases, it became more pronounced. Additional analysis revealed that factors such as obesity, metabolic syndrome, diabetes, and anemia partially mediate the

HMB-CVD relationship. However, the direct association is stronger than the indirect one, suggesting an independent pathophysiological mechanism linking HMB to heart disease.

In older women, heavy bleeding was no longer as clearly associated with increased cardiovascular risk, which resulted from different underlying causes of bleeding. After adjusting for risk factors, the association was weaker and only affected certain conditions in older women. This indicates that the effect of HMB on cardiovascular risk is most pronounced in young women and may diminish with age, when other risk factors come to the fore and the etiology of bleeding becomes more related to structural changes, such as fibroids.

The study clearly indicates that heavy menstrual bleeding is an independent and significant risk factor for cardiovascular disease, particularly in young women. HMB without irregular cycles appears to be even stronger than HMB with IM. The researchers' conclusions suggest that menstrual flow intensity may be an important clinical signal worth considering when assessing cardiovascular health. This is particularly true for young women, in whom this disturbance may reflect processes occurring in the circulatory system at a very early stage.

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METRICS

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- Submission to first decision (median) 3 days
- Downloads 8M (2024)
- Citations 9

The reviewed article aims to present the relationship between heavy menstrual bleeding and cardiovascular diseases, which is related to the journal's modern approach to medicine.